

ANALYSIS OF THE FEMALE IMAGE IN WORKS OF FINE ART

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Abstract. *The image of a woman in the worldviews of the peoples of the world and the image of the image of a woman and mother in the portrait genre in the works of artists are described. The traditional worldviews of historical periods and the evolution of ideas and trends related to women's issues that arose during these periods were studied. It is important to consider the problem of women from the point of view of the traditional worldview. This is because trends and stereotypes about the social role of women are traditionally formed based on deeply rooted ideas passed down from generation to generation. These concepts have evolved over the long history of society and have historical, social, economic, political, cultural, and religious aspects. Since the central core of all this is the worldview of people, it is important to analyze the image of women in the traditional worldview. This allows us to understand the evolutionary path of understanding women's problems and their basis in society. The color scheme in the works, the position of the images, and their interpretation are also discussed.*

Keywords: *female image, traditional Uzbek worldview, feminine essence, psychology, colors, fine arts, artistic and aesthetic thinking.*

There are eternal themes in the fine arts of different eras. One of them is the theme of women, the theme of motherhood. Each era has its ideal of a woman, which is reflected in how women have been recognized throughout human history, and what myths have surrounded her and helped create. In all centuries and eras, the female image has attracted special attention from artists and has attracted and will continue to attract.

In our national history, there have been many women who led a nation, mothers who led an entire tribe, heroes who were famous for their bravery, women who were famous for their sacred qualities, famous speakers, famous musicians, and artists. Some of them were forgotten in the course of history, and some are still preserved in the memory of the people through legends and tales and have become a source of monuments of national spirituality.

According to legends and tales, it is associated with women, it is easy to see that the traditional gender position of the Uzbeks, the place of a woman in society is highly valued by her characteristics, such as wisdom and loyalty.

In the world of fine art, "Lady with an Ermine" by Leonardo da Vinci, "Mona Lisa Gioconda", I. Kramskoy, "Notorious Glory", "Thoughts of a Mother" by Rakhim Akhmedov, "Boysun Madonna" by Rozi Choriev, and of course "Laili" by Kamoliddin Bekhzod, Zukhra. , Shirin, his devoted love, they were bright figures in people's thoughts and dreams.

Although the famous Italian artist Leonardo da Vinci, one of the brightest representatives of the Renaissance, devoted many studies, novels, and poems to this masterpiece of world art, this painting is still shrouded in mystery and continues to attract millions of people. The mysterious smile of Gioconda, the lady depicted in the work, captivates everyone; the name of the woman whose portrait was created remains a mystery.

It is not for nothing that Leonardo da Vinci's work "La Gioconda" is described as a symbol of pictorial art, a living symbol reflecting the spirit of Renaissance culture.

Perhaps the square hall of the Louvre (the Museum of Universal Art in Paris), where this painting is kept, this palace full of admiration, this place where masterpieces of fine art have found a place, can accommodate such unbridled passions? Look, be sure to watch "Gioconda"! You will see an image that is stored at a temperature of 25 degrees Celsius and is taken for medical examination once a year during convoy surveillance. Now it is an object of worship, not only a symbol of painting but also a smiling image. Of course, the artist who created it, Leonardo da Vinci, whose name is full of pride, is also recognized.

This woman's name was Mona Lisa Gherardini del Giocondo, maybe Isabella Gualando, Isabella d'Este, Philiberta of Savoy, Constance d'Avalos... Who else do you know?

The unknown origin of the woman in the photo helps her become famous. This painting has been shrouded in mystery for centuries. The portrait of this "lady of the court with a transparent veil draped over her shoulders" has been an adornment of the royal collection for many years. The painting "La Gioconda" can sometimes be seen in the bed of Madame de Maintenon, and sometimes in Napoleon's palace in the Tuileries. When Louis XIII was a more playful baby, he did not want to part with this painting hanging in the Grand Gallery, he did not want to give it to the Duke of Buckingham: "It is impossible to part with this work, which is considered the best in the world." Everywhere - in castles and city apartments - noble families tried to teach their daughters the art of imitating the famous smile of Gioconda. This work became the basis for the emergence of an entire school of art, which inspired such talented painters as Raphael, Ingres, David, and Corot. This image has always worried and excited a person. The historian Michel wrote: "He attracted me like a rabbit on a hook." Since the end of the 19th century, letters expressing love and sympathy began to be sent to Gioconda. This situation causes a very important event in the history of the work - its disappearance and rediscovery.

Freud's opinion also became known: "Gioconda's smile is the smile of the artist's mother." In this regard, de Sade's definition is unique: "She is the embodiment of feminine virtue." [1]

By the end of the 17th century, Russian portraiture had achieved truly remarkable development. One of the main themes here is the celebration of the ideal image of a woman. The artist, first of all, had to depict the beauty of a woman, no matter what. The women in these portraits present a flirtatious and attractive portrait of an unknown woman, incorporating genre elements and traditions of portraiture in art. He was wearing a black fur and velvet coat, a fur hat, and leather gloves. A woman sits in an open carriage on the Anichkov Bridge in St. Petersburg.

However, "Portrait of an Unknown Woman" created a sensation at its first exhibition, more because of the subject matter than because of the aesthetics of the work. Several critics suggested that the woman was a prostitute. One critic described the painting as "a coquette in a carriage,"

while another wrote of "a provocatively beautiful woman, dressed in velvet and fur, looking at you from a luxurious carriage." allowed the wicked women of big cities to take to the streets."

Kramskoy noted: "Some say that this woman is unknown. Is she good or for sale? But she has a whole era in her." [2]

Any image is based on national character. National character is formed based on the specific psychological structure of the population. The socio-historical, as well as geographical environment, reflects the originality and specificity of art and literature, primarily through the national psychological structure.

To penetrate deeper into the manifestation of national character, it is necessary to determine the reasons for the formation and growth of a nation in each aspect of this national character. For example, such character traits of Uzbek women as fortitude, simplicity, brotherhood, hospitality, and gentleness are characteristic of our ancestors and have not lost their essence to this day.

Speaking about the image of a woman as a symbol of beauty and elegance, we should not forget that every nation has its characteristics in the perception of beauty.

In general, the level of culture of any nation is reflected in the care for women in society, as well as in the attitude of Uzbeks toward women as wives, mothers, and daughters.

Women are amazing and mysterious creatures who have been sung by poets and artists since time immemorial. It's no secret that this has been and remains a favorite topic that attracts creative people. This is confirmed by the excellent selection of female images in works of different movements, because each era had its ideal, reflecting not only the girl's appearance but also her psyche.

Uzbek fine art is no exception. Uzbek art with long periods - history of Uzbekistan, change of generations, management systems; These are centuries of changes in customs and worldviews. Naturally, during this period the ideal of a woman and female beauty changed, which is reflected in this picture.

The female image has always attracted special attention from artists. Female images created in portrait art embody the poetic ideal in the harmonious unity of her spiritual qualities and physical appearance. From portraits, we can determine how social events, fashion, literature, art, and painting itself influence a woman's appearance and her mental structure.

In the portrait genre, the image of a woman, a mother, is an immortal, ancient, and beloved image. In fine art, the image of a woman is depicted as love, loyalty, fidelity, will, perseverance, patience, and continuation of life. Since ancient times, in the countries of the East and Europe, the image of a woman has been revered as a symbol of beauty, elegance, and love. We can see the image of a woman, a mother in the works of almost all artists. Examples of this are Usta Momin, A. Volkov, P. Benkov, M. Nabiev, A. Abdullaev, L. Abdullaev, Ch. Akhmarov, B. Jalolov, R. Akhmedov, A. Nur and others.

Especially in the works of Rakhim Akhmedov, we can see a very impressive and vivid expressiveness of the image of the mother. It will not be an exaggeration to say that "Morning of Motherhood" is one of the artist's masterpieces. The work depicts a Uzbek woman nursing a sweetly sleeping child in her warm arms at a wonderful moment in the morning. In the work, the harmony of man and nature is shown without decoration; the viewer is attracted by the image of a woman in a green dress, with a scarf flowing from her head, with two hairs thrown over her shoulders. The world of the homeland is shown in the mental state of a woman, a calm, happy mother, the family is shown in the bosom of Mother Nature. The main elements of the image are

nature, the mother, dawn, and the baby. That is, the beauty of nature, mother, child, and morning means the beauty of the whole world. [3]

First of all, for a person, a mother is a holy being. We see everything good and beloved from our mother and receive our first education from her. For a mother, there is no person more valuable than her child. Rakhim Akhmedov's work "Mother's Thoughts" fills a person with deep thoughts. In this work, it is clear from the mother's eyes that she is waiting for her child's path. In addition, the mother's hands lived and worked for her children and family all her life. The Uzbek courtyard, depicted behind the mother's back, also attracted art lovers, plastered courtyards, and we see that this place has not been touched by a man's hand for a long time, and we see sadness and pain in the mother's eyes. In Gavde, the "silhouette" is depicted with great skill in blue, purple, pink, green, and yellow tones against the background of a landscape in clear, light colors. No separation in the world would be more difficult for a mother than the loss of a child, and the fact that the artist wonderfully expresses this pain and this grief through art increases people's admiration. It is worth noting that all these reasons revealed the whole essence of this image and were reflected in one work. [4]

This charm creates the basis for a true depiction of the original nature, thatched walls and narrow streets of old Khiva, breathing life. The gaze of a true artist is very sharp. He deeply feels moments that an ordinary person often cannot reach, and expresses them vividly with his brush. These are exactly the dots in Momo Holzhan's portrait; every wrinkle on Momo's face tells the story of her hard work and a life full of worries, where she courageously overcame difficult trials. Just look at his simple clothes and thoughtful look. If I say that this work represents a generalized image of all the contemporaries and contemporaries of Mama Kholzhan, the hardworking women of Khorezm, then it will probably be correct. [5]

Meaningful beautiful eyes and cherry lips of a fairy at work, the silence of a magnificent palace filled with the aroma of oriental pleasures and juices, precious jewelry sparkling in the dice, a wave of jewelry, original stones, the light of a burning turquoise mane, a beautiful reflection of silver and the mysterious look of the Queen of the Great Ancient Planet. This look at the soft edges of the spring steppe, the play of the sun's rays, the corners of cool, graceful gardens, the pleasant smell of ripe peaches, short moonlit nights, the sharp aromas of mint blowing on the wings. winds from endless deserts. This is the place of short moonlit nights. This is my view of Asia," says the artist about his work. He always has a place in the heart of everyone born in this ancient land of

Uzbekistan. A person is inspired by the beauty of this look and lives to bow before its greatness...[6]

Social, economic, political, and cultural changes and modernization in modern society have a unique effect on the formation of the image of an Uzbek woman. The image of an Uzbek woman in the past had different characteristics. Mythological, religious, philosophical, and literary interpretations were given to his images by the historical and cultural development of each period. As a result, the image of a woman is symbolically reflected in narratives, epics, folklore, fiction, and works of art. In the works of poets, the images of the motherland, beautiful, man, good wife, and bad wife are created and sung. In the Uzbek worldview, knowing the value of words and the value of the country is the main quality of a good woman, while a good woman should also know the value of a man and the characteristics of a bad woman, on the contrary, it is disrespectful to her husband.

"The image of a modern Uzbek woman shows signs of tradition and postmodernism". "One of the modern tendencies of Uzbek women in the modern society is to strive to be postmodern. It is aimed not at life with its postmodern conditions, but at being postmodern as a person." [7]

Today, all national cultures are fully aware of the influence of the process of globalization and its "children's" mass culture. There is no doubt that traditional values and symbolic images inherited from ancient times are changing radically, including the image of women in the modern Uzbek mentality. At the same time, the role of the Uzbek woman in modern culture and social activities has led to the formation of new images, along with the change of centuries-old images in traditional consciousness.

Preserving the positive traditional aspects of a woman's appearance is one of the important issues for the people. Works of fine art, which are carriers of folk cultural values, today play an important role in creating the image of an Uzbek woman. Because under the influence of art, especially fine art, women imitate images and try to create their images. The influence of globalization on the image of the Uzbek woman in modern culture cannot be denied, but if you study the relationship between tradition and innovation in the image of our contemporaries, it becomes obvious that the traditional national character dominates.

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